

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D10.5

Ethic report on ASRY3 and Assessment report for AWPY4 OEI - Requirement No. 7

WP1 — T1.4

Partnership
FOR THE
Assessment
OF
Risks
FROM
Chemicals

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Document history

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1	08/01/2025	N/A	First draft prepared for MB review
3	01/04/2025	N/A	Revised version based on MB feedback
4	23/04/2025	N/A	Revised version integrating last comments (PARC CT, DEPB experts & T1.4 co-leaders)

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Abstract

This deliverable Ethics report (D10.5) has two main objectives:

- Firstly, this deliverable revisits the activities performed during the third year of PARC, planned in the AWPY3 (1st May 2024 to 30th April 2025) highlighting issues faced / addressed with regards to ethics; it concerns activities that have already occurred.
- Secondly, it provides an ethical assessment for the activities that will be implemented during the fourth year of PARC and which are described in the AWPY4 (1st of May 2025 to 30th April 2026);

This Ethics report builds on the preceding reports D10.2, D10.3 and D10.4 which provided an assessment of the activities that were to be implemented in the preceding years of PARC.

Key Words

Ethics, DEPB, Challenges, data, human studies, animal experimentation, artificial intelligence, AI, Machine-learning

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Authors and Acknowledgements

This deliverable has been prepared by Basile Cazalis de Fondouce (ANSES) as part of the work of the PARC Coordination Team under the supervision of the T1.4 co-leaders, Lucija Perharic (NIJZ) and Philippe Marin (EHESP) and on the basis of the D10.4 to ensure follow-up and continuity for the ethics reports. Other members of the PARC Coordination Team have provided valuable insights for the revision and refinement of this deliverable.

It has then been sent to the PARC Management Board for review and refinement as well as to the PARC DEPB before being finalised for submission based on the feedback received.

Acronyms

Acronym	Reference
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AOP	Adverse Outcome Pathway
BPA	Bisphenol-A
DEPB	Data and Ethics Protection Board
DMP	Data Management Plan
EDC	Endocrine Disrupting Chemical
EWS	Early Warning System
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GB	Governing Board
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GMO	Genetically Modified Organism
GSB	Grant Signatory Board
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HBM-GV	HBM - Guidance Value
IB	International Board
JRC	Joint Research Center
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
MB	Management Board
MCRA	Monte Carlo Risk Assessment
ML	Machine-Learning
NAMs	New Approach Methodologies
NGRA	Next Generation Risk Assessment
NH	National Hubs
PARC CT	PARC Coordination Team
PFAS	Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
3Rs	Replacement, Reduction and Refinement
RA	Risk Assessment
SF	Stakeholder Forum
SOP	Standard Operating Procedures
TRV	Toxic Reference Value
WP	Work Package

Glossary

N/A

1 — Ethics overview in year 3

1.1 Introduction

The third and fourth years of PARC are significant as we reach the midterm of the partnership. Key activities are now in full swing and notable achievements have been reached:

1: A list of priority research topics for the second phase of the Partnership

- The prioritisation process has resulted in a list of ranked priority topics for the next few years of PARC.
- These priorities will guide the partners in initiating new research and research and innovation projects.

2: Support for the Commission in preparing its roadmap for phasing out animal testing in chemical safety assessments

- PARC roadmap for the implementation of the Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA) was communicated and discussed as part of the preparation of the roadmap for phasing out animal testing in chemical safety assessments.
- The ten principles guiding the implementation of the NGRA support the conduct of change towards the implementation of new approaches and methodologies.

3: Launch of the European HBM survey

- Human Biomonitoring (HBM)-aligned studies targeting the general population have progressed to the sampling phase in one of three population groups across various countries.
- In Germany, the sampling phase for adults has been completed. Final effect biomarkers & health outcomes that will be followed are selected.

4: Occupational exposure

- Sampling campaigns are expected to be fully underway in 2025.
- Occupational healthcare project focuses on hazardous medicinal products, inhalation anaesthetics, and disinfection/cleaning products. Exposure will be studied in 11 countries. Similar project on waste management sector.

5. Derivation of HBM — GV

- Human biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for the general population and/or for workers have been derived for acetamiprid, aluminium and its inorganic compounds, chromium VI, nickel, phthalates (DEHPT, DINP) pyrethroids (gamma cyhalothrin), UV filters (Uvinul A plus, benzophenone)
- Derivations of HBM-GVs for the general population and/or for workers for arsenic and its inorganic compounds, lithium, mercury (elemental, inorganic and methyl-mercury), imidacloprid, deltamethrin and pyrethroid metabolites are in progress.

6: Environmental monitoring pilot studies

- More than 200 samples were collected throughout the EU covering 4 matrices and different scenarios and reference sites to analyse Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals (EDCs).
- Data covering up to 70 different Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) is currently being collected in a harmonised protocol. PFAS case studies focus on PFAS emission sources and subsequent pathways to the aquatic environment, with particular interest in the role of precursors.

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7: Human biomonitoring data accessible in integrative exposure assessment models

- HBM study owners generate regulatory relevant results using human biomonitoring data for combined exposure to mixtures of chemicals. Harmonisation is achieved by using the MCRA software, which is part of the PARC toolbox.
- The toolbox allows aggregated and mixed exposures. It has been presented to risk assessment agencies and risk managers.

8: 1st report listing New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) used in PARC

- For human health, a list of the assays organised according to the five prioritised endpoints under development among the PARC projects has been published.
- For the environment, some NAMs have been described for hazard assessment.

9: Reviewing substance-specific Risk Assessment (RA) depending on intended use

- Case studies reviewing selected methodologies and approaches for regulatory RA have been finalised. A mapping of substances subject to assessment in multiple legal frameworks was done.
- Inconsistencies in the regulation of antimicrobial substances were identified, as well as existing and missing links between different pieces of chemicals legislation.

10: A first catalogue of analytical laboratories

- The first Europe-wide catalogue of analytical laboratories for human biomonitoring and environmental monitoring has been published online. This catalogue facilitates access to competent laboratories for setting up research or monitoring studies.

11: Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD)

- The SSbD toolbox was computationally implemented in version 0.1, which features a comprehensive suite of tools and databases for conducting safety and sustainability assessments.

Regarding ethics development, the year 3 was the opportunity to further communicate on relevant Chemical RA ethics issues to the consortium (12/12/2024 ethics workshop) as well as to refine and outline PARC ethics processes.

No major ethics concerns have been identified / reported / faced during the months 24-36, though the use and potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI) / Machine Learning (ML) for Chemical Risk Assessment received increased attention. Consequently, further assessment of PARC activities and follow-up discussion are foreseen in early 2025 to ensure a responsible use of AI/ML in PARC activities.

The Annual Summary Report for the third year (ASRY3) and the Annual Work Plan for the fourth year (AWPY4) complement this Ethics assessment.

1.2 T1.4 & DEPB activities

During the third year, T1.4 and the DEPB have been active in support to the partnership and the partners to monitor ethics development and proactively raise awareness of ethics issues.

In addition to regular email communication, T1.4 leadership and the PARC CT met twice in dedicated meetings (30/08/2024, 26/11/2024). A DEPB meeting was organised (06/12/2024) and DEPB members had the opportunity to participate and discuss during the Consortium Meeting (13-16/05/2024).

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In addition, members of the DEPB were actively involved (including external experts as speakers) in the ethics workshop “Emerging and conventional ethical concerns in the next-generation chemical risk assessment” (12/12/2024) with presentations on ethics-relevant thematic such as AI, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), Data management and human involvement, ethical aspects of biobanking, use of human biological samples in in-vitro studies, and animal experiments (slides available [here](#) for PARC members).

DEPB External experts were also involved in the review of deliverables and projects (e.g., AD9.1, P6.4.2.e), as well as this report.

1.3 Human involvement in PARC activities

General involvement of external human participants in PARC activities:

Like in previous years, PARC activities during the third year have involved human participants in the setting-up and implementation of activities (ex: researchers) and for the management of the partnership.

Beyond PARC participants which have been logically included in the preparation/implementation of the activities (their involvement in activities is not detailed in this document), external participants¹ have been involved in selected activities of PARC. For these instances, the participation has been on a voluntary basis and the participants have been informed of the objectives and expectations for their participation.

First of all, ‘general’ activities involving external participants during the second year have taken place across all WPs. Such transversal activities include:

- The preparation and dissemination of various surveys (e.g., ‘Mapping of needs process’ sent to the Governing Board members, Stakeholder Forum, International Board, which was finalised during Y3, yearly WP3 focus groups, etc.);
- The implementation of various boards (Stakeholder Forum, International Board, National Hubs, DEPB, etc.) with online and physical meetings held during the third year;
- The development of synergies with like-minded initiatives and partners (ex: finalisation of agreement with the NORMAN Association, collaboration with JRC on PARC specific projects, organisation of two SYNnet forum, etc.);
- The organisation of workshops/meetings/consultations with stakeholders (note: not in the framework of the Stakeholder forum; ex: GB workshops which were opened to external participants from PARC participating organisations).

Human volunteers for Human biomonitoring studies:

As mentioned above, the most significant research activity regarding this topic is the HBM studies (under WP4) with the recruitment of voluntary participants and the collection of samples started in Y2 and continued in Y3. This includes classic sampling procedures and materials (notably blood and urine) as well as innovative (and less invasive) methods of collection such as use of silicon wristbands and dried blood spots samples.

¹ External participants: participants not working in an organisation which is a member of the PARC consortium. It includes both (i) individuals with indirect links to PARC (ex: PARC GB members, PARC SF or PARC IB) and (ii) individuals with no links to PARC (ex: volunteers recruited for HBM general survey).

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For both the classical and innovative approaches, Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) have been developed, as well as ethics due process (collection of ethics approval at the local level, informed consent forms, etc.) has been followed for the collection, processing, storage and disposal of the materials.

Following up on year 2, PARC activities have continued with the sampling phase (on a voluntary basis) for the general population HBM survey (P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO) in one or more of the three population groups (children, teenagers, or adults) across various countries, including Poland, Denmark, Belgium, Norway, Estonia, and Israel, while sampling efforts have continued in Slovenia and Poland. In Germany, the sampling phase for adults has been completed.

Likewise, the occupational studies (4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP-TTL and P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthcareSurvey_TTL_RUMC), are progressing well, with protocols finalised, training materials prepared, and ethical approvals obtained in several countries. Sampling campaigns are expected to be fully underway by early 2025.

In the framework of the HBM studies (general population survey and occupational surveys), PARC plan to collect and analyse 'biological matrices' such as blood, hair and urine.

Focus Group and Citizen surveys

Most Europeans are concerned about exposure to chemicals in their daily lives and have doubts regarding the safety of various products. A recent cross-sectional observational qualitative study investigating Europeans' public concerns about chemicals emphasized the need for more accessible and understandable information for all citizens. Among its goals, PARC aims to gather more in-depth information about citizens' needs, perceptions, and concerns regarding chemicals and other related topics, and to develop targeted communication materials aimed at addressing these issues effectively.

As part of the PARC project, both focus groups and citizen surveys are being conducted in partner countries. In the first round of focus groups, Finland, Latvia, Portugal, and Sweden participated. Two focus groups were hosted in each country between May and July 2024. A predefined script guided semi-structured discussions, covering topics aligned with the study's objectives. Key topics included a brief presentation of PARC, sources of exposure, types of products of most concern, substances of concern, health concerns, preferred sources of information about chemicals, protective behaviors, and priority areas of research for PARC. This deliverable describes the results at the country level and highlights several common themes that emerged from the eight focus groups. Additional focus groups will be launched in the coming years to provide a more comprehensive understanding.

The questions for the citizen survey were developed by reviewing previous surveys on citizens' perceptions and concerns about chemicals. The representative survey will be launched in the PARC countries in 2025.

By exploring citizens' awareness, concerns, and information needs, both the focus groups and the citizen survey will contribute to strengthening communication strategies within and beyond PARC.

1.4 Human cells / tissues

In the framework of the HBM studies (general population survey and occupational surveys), PARC is collecting and analysing 'biological matrices' such as blood and urine. It is not directly considered as 'human cells / tissues', but it is nevertheless pertinent to highlight their use in this section.

Use of human cells / tissues during Toxicology analysis:

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As hazard assessment (notably on human health) is a key aspect of PARC, the use of human cells / tissues is required for much of PARC’s research activities. The availability and access to these human cells / tissues is managed in line with relevant legislation and ethical considerations.

Hazard assessment projects under WP5 required the use of human cells / tissues for their research activities during Y3. Similar care in the procurement and handling of human cells / tissues have been ensured (for example, ensuring that cells lines used are legal and obtained from legitimate sources).

For instance, this notably includes the use of human cells / tissues to fill toxicity data gaps (ex: on subforms of the mycotoxins Enniatins and *Alternaria* for human health (P5.1.1.a_Y1_Toxins_BfR_UNIVIE, using for instance the MCF-7 cell line) which started in Y2 and continued in Y3; Bisphenol A (BPA) adverse outcomes on human health) though due process for sourcing the human cells have occasionally caused delays and led to the extension of the project to M48.

1.5 Animal experimentation

PARC is committed to reduce — as much as possible — the reliance on animal experimentation in line with the 3 Rs (Replace, Reduce, Refine). Many PARC activities are indeed contributing to the development and recognition of animal-free approaches.

Nevertheless, some animal experimentation is still necessary for the development of new methods as reference, for hazard identification, RA and to drive adequate regulatory update. Consequently, during Y2 onwards, PARC has initiated animal experimentation under WP5 research activities (see table 1 below)

In support of the European Commission’s preparation of the ‘roadmap for phasing out animal testing in chemical safety assessments’, PARC has been involved in the discussion organised by the European Commission (in working groups on human health and on environment). In addition, PARC has worked on a draft PARC roadmap for the implementation of the NGRARoute (more information available in AD2.1). This PARC document has notably been acknowledged in two documents published by the European Commission in 2024².

Table 1: Overview of animal experimentation in PARC activities in Y3

Project	Animal-based assay	Context	Partner	Project duration
P5.1.2.b BPA alternatives - environment	Fish short-term reproduction assay OECD TG 229/230 <i>Lymnaea stagnalis</i> embryos Zebrafish embryos	A short-term screening for estrogenic and androgenic activity and aromatase inhibition. Part of a battery of tests applied to investigate the potential endocrine disrupting related effects of “real-life” mixtures of BPA alternatives on different species or organisms	INERIS (FR)	M1-M48 (ongoing)

² 1) European Commission (2024): Proposal to establish a Subgroup on Test Methods in CARACAL. In 52nd Meeting of the Competent Authorities for REACH and CLP (CARACAL). <https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/a0b483a2-4c05-4058-addf-2a4de71b9a98/library/4fa23357-4bbb-4f8f-a46b-fa9b784a7300/details>

2) European Commission, Cronin M (2024): Report of the European Commission workshop on “The Roadmap Towards Phasing Out Animal Testing for Chemical Safety Assessments” — Brussels, 11-12 December 2023. Edited by: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2873/34576>

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		Partner UU (SE) reported problems in carrying out their originally planned experiments (effects on adipocyte development in zebrafish) and proposed using Alamar blue assay adapted for zebrafish embryos as alternative.		
P5.2.1.a NAMs NGTxCs	Whole organism (zebrafish) test model for oxidative stress	Reference compounds have been tested in zebrafish for induction of oxidative stress applying a specific fluorescent dye with different protocols to optimize the protocols and identify most suitable timepoints of analysis	RIVM (NL)	M1-M60 (ongoing)
5.2.1.c EDTh Disruption	Rodent reproductive toxicity study (studying TBBPA and PFOS substances) Rat non-Genetically Modified Organism (GMO)	Apical endpoints were measured and a comprehensive collection of samples was established to conduct detailed molecular investigations of underlying effect mechanism. -The rat <i>in vivo</i> data and the human <i>in vitro</i> , (generated by VUB in the same project), will be combined with data from fish embryo and snails to understand species differences and the relation between <i>in vivo</i> and <i>in vitro</i> data. studying TBBPA and PFOS substances)- Combined DNT endpoints sensitive to THSD in zebrafish 5 days post hatching (dph), including behaviour and brain and eye morphology, will be evaluated after exposure to BPA alternatives, BPE, BPAP, and BPS-MAE	DTU (DK)	M1-M48 (ongoing)
5.2.1.d Immunotox	Respiratory sensitization of mice Mice non-GMO	Exposure to known respiratory sensitizer chemicals (chloramineT, piperazine) to induce respiratory allergy in mice. This assay explores toxicity on lung-derived dendritic cells using a variety of cellular, biochemical and omics methods with a focus on antigen uptake and presentation and on characterizing extracellular vesicles. Although these studies are relevant for respiratory immunotoxicity and sensitization they are also relevant for immunosuppression and response to antigen.	NPHC (HU)	M1-M48 (ongoing)
5.2.1.d Immunotox	Immunosuppression and response to vaccination on mice Mice non-GMO	Using mice as a model, the response to an influenza vaccine will be monitored in the presence or absence of chemicals (toxins, PFAS). Cellular and omics studies will be conducted.	INSERM (FR)	M1-M48 (ongoing)

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		In parallel, the impact of chemicals on primary PBMC (e.g. T cells) activated or not by antigens (e.g. recall antigens) will be monitored using similar omics and cellular methods as well as extracellular vesicles characterization.		
5.3.4.a PBK kinetics, (Case study 6)	Rat study — exposure to enniatin B Rat non-GMO	An <i>in vivo</i> Toxicokinetic experiment on Sprague-Dawley rats was realized by Anses (IV/oral cross-over on 8 Sprague-Dawley rats in order to analyse parent compound and determination of metabolites.	ANSES (FR)	M1-M48 (ongoing)

1.6 Data use and processing

PARC activities in year 3 include the collection and use of personal data for the realisation of the activities of the partnership and may include sensitive personal data (specifically genetic data, health-related data and biometric data).

For the purpose of the partnership management, an up-to-date contacts list of the different PARC boards and participants is maintained. Request for addition as well as for deletion have been processed in the contact list.

Many activities have worked to identify useable data sources, databases and datasets. Due processes for the (re)use of data have been followed/are ongoing (e.g., getting approval from Data owners, making sure that data can be reused based on reuse licence information, verifying consent for further use for personal data, establishing GDPR-compliant protocol for reuse, etc.).

Furthermore, the PARC Data Management Plan (DMP) (D7.1) has been prepared by WP7 during the first year of the partnership, and during year 3 was supplemented by the project-level DMPs and an updated version of the PARC-level DMP is being developed (deliverable report due in October 2025). This updated deliverable is intended to provide guidance for the implementation of a FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) approach toward the use and management of data (either produced by PARC or from outside sources).

In addition, with the support of the GOfAIR Foundation and the WP9, data experts from PARC partners have been trained in data FAIRness.

In Y3, PARC partners have developed and implemented access to national HBM data in the exposure simulation tool Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA).

This collaborative effort between RA agencies and PARC partners involved in HBM studies has made these data more FAIR: findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable, while complying with the rules of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the transparency regulation³.

1.7 Artificial Intelligence

³ Transparency Regulation — 06/09/2019 - REGULATION (EU) 2019/1381 on the transparency and sustainability of the EU risk assessment in the food chain available [here](#).

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PARC use Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) as tools to power and/or support PARC research activities. Indeed, AI and ML have many valuable applications for Chemical RA and management and - provided that they are used responsibly - can help bring forward the NGRA (Kleinstreuer and Hartung, 2024).

The topic of AI/ML and its implication for Chemical RA and management was also stressed during both GB and DEPBB meetings in Y3. Further to this discussion, PARC is looking to organise intra-PARC discussion on how AI/ML can be used in a useful and ethical manner. In the first instance, the WP7 co-leads (Iseult Lynch and Stijn Baken) have been appointed to liaise with the European Commission on scoping a PARC AI strategy. This should be done in parallel to the organisation a dedicated workshop outlining PARC AI use for the GB. Those are expected end of Y3 / beginning of Y4.

Overall, some PARC participants have been using 'general-use' AI systems in a supporting capacity. For instance, this includes text-support AI systems (generation of summaries, highlight of key information, etc.) with chatbot (ex : ChatGPT, NotebookLM) as well as scientific publication screening (ex: ASreview).

Furthermore, PARC activities in Y3 included assessment of the potential of AI systems as supporting technology for chemical RA.

- P4.3.1.d is notably working on data processing methodology and to allow for a swifter interpretation of existing data for research and support to policy purposes. In Y3 specifically, a collaborative trial leveraging three environmental, food and human datasets was implemented to define ranges of acceptable thresholds for the QAQC pre-processing and to help for the tools pre-selection.

- P6.4.2.c conducted a survey "Landscape and readiness of computational NAMs based on ML and AI approaches for chemicals' NGRA" at end of Y2-beginning of Y3 and then analysed the survey results. In parallel, the project implemented a review aimed at the production of a framework for more transparent reporting of predictions obtained using AI/ML models for regulatory purposes by the end of Y3. Other scientific publications & conference presentation on AI/ML potential were published/performed.

- T8.2 has seen the literature analysis of existing AI systems in Early Warning Systems (EWS) and the summarising overview in the context of their reliability and usefulness for chemicals prioritisation regarding toxicity.

In the third year, several activities related to AI have also relied on direct use of AI systems for research activities.

- In P5.3.1.a, the objective is to validate innovative in silico and bioinformatics approaches for quantitative chemical hazard assessment and will lead to the development of system toxicology tools for regulators which will be powered by AI to parse through high quantity of data.

- In P5.3.2.a, Y3 saw the ongoing development of AI and text mining tools supporting AOP development (notably through the development or improvement of advanced computational approaches).

- In P7.3.3.a, the initial text mining software review done in Y2 was followed up with the ongoing development of AI-based text mining tools (to rank, extract and visualise pertinent information) for the AOP development.

- T8.2 has worked on the definition of metabolomics-based biomarkers with computational tools that allow their proper interpretation using as AI methods and advanced bioinformatics algorithms.

- In A7.3.4, ML has also been used to improve pharmacophore modelling.

A workshop on modelling activities in PARC is notably being organised by WP5, WP6 and WP7 colleagues and will be held in Estonia on 9-11 June 2025.

1.8 Environment, health and safety

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During the second year, no activities with significant potential risk for the environment or for the health and safety of participants have been identified.

Some research activities (notably under WP5 and WP4) have used harmful or potentially harmful chemicals to investigate substances and mixtures and their impact on environmental and human health. These experiments (and the processing and disposal of hazardous materials) were (and will be) however implemented following good practices and adapted lab procedures to prevent any risks of contamination for the environment, or on the health of the researchers involved.

During Y3, PARC has instead implemented dedicated activities for environmental program monitoring within two pilot studies.

- The first one (P5.2.1.b) address EDCs which were analysed in air, water, soil and biota (fish), using a combination of bioassays, target analyses and suspect screening (ideally covering the full EDC list)

More than 200 samples were collected throughout the EU covering 4 matrices and different scenarios and reference sites.

- The second one (P4.2.a) studies PFAS with a baseline study using existing monitoring data on diffuse PFAS contamination, as well as a series of case studies focusing on the transport and transformation of PFAS from known sources to aquatic recipients.

Data covering up to 70 different PFAS is currently being collected in a harmonised protocol. While the PFAS baseline study addresses diffuse PFAS contamination in the environment, the PFAS case studies focus on PFAS emission sources and subsequent pathways to the aquatic environment, with particular interest in the role of precursors.

1.9 Involvement of non-EU countries

Like during the previous year, non-EU countries have been involved in the activities of PARC (Iceland, Norway, Switzerland, Israel, UK) across several WPs. PARC participants are aware that they have to ensure that the activities performed in non-EU countries will remain in line with at least one EU member state's legislations, that they should obtain local ethics approval in non-EU countries and that local population should also benefit from the outcomes of the activities.

In addition, collaboration and networking is not limited by the EU boundaries over the duration of PARC. Involvement of experts is also valid for countries in the wider European region and OECD countries. For instance, the International Board (IB) set up in the first year includes non-EU members from the United States, Canada, Japan and South Africa.

2 Ethics assessment for year 4

2.1 General assessment for Y4

Of particular interest, the fourth year (1st May 2025 to 30th April 2026) will see the sampling phase of the human volunteers in the HBM studies (including the collection of biological samples and health data). Careful consideration by the PARC actors involved will be crucial to meet high ethical standards and to ensure that volunteers are treated with respect and that their concerns are taken into account.

Beyond ongoing projects and transversal activities that have been started in previous years, eighteen new projects will start during Y4 and one Rapid Response Mechanism (RRM) project was included in the workflow in the middle of Y3.

The flagged ethics concerns table (annex 1) has been updated to include Y4 projects and any changes for ongoing projects.

Table 2 provides a succinct overview of the projects foreseen for a start in the fourth year. In the same vein, table 3 highlight the projects / cases studies whose conclusion is scheduled in Y4.

Table 2: New projects starting Y4

Project ID	Schedule
P.2.1.a_Y3MnHexP-RRM_UBA Mono-n-hexyl phthalate, extent of exposure and potential sources	M29-M76
P4.1.1.3.a_Y4_PFAS Mother milk_LNS_BPI PFAS in Mother Milk: pregnancy and postnatal health	M37-M81
P4.1.1.3.b_Y4_PFASChildren_SpF Description of PFAS Exposure in early life in European countries	M37-M81
P4.1.1.3.c_Y4_TimePatternEU_VITO Time patterns of internal human exposure to environmental pollutants in Europe	M37-M72
P4.1.3.1.b_Y4_Health-based-IA-GV_LNS_NCPHP Derivation of Health-based Indoor Air Guideline Values	M37-M81
P4.2.d_Y4_Siloxanes_AU_INERIS Volatile siloxanes in the European environment — towards robust data in support of regulatory action	M37-M60
P5.1.1.d_Y4_PlasticLeach_NIPH Hazard characterization of leachable chemicals present in plastics	M37-M81
P5.1.2.c_Y4_TG+MP_ANSES* Microplastic bioaccumulation datagaps and applicability of in vitro bioaccumulation assessment methods	M37-M60
P5.2.a_Y4_RegNAMs_ANSES	M37-M81

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Regulatory readiness of NAMs	
P5.2.1.f_Y4_DART-ED_DTU Developmental and Reproductive Toxicity - Endocrine Disruption	M37-M81
P5.2.1.g_Y4_DIT-NAM_INSERTM Developmental Immunotoxicity - NAM development	M37-M81
P5.2.1.h_Y4_SDHEPATOX_ANSES Sexual dimorphism associated to susceptibility to hepatotoxicity of environmental contaminants	M37-M60
P5.3.1.b_Y4_grOMICS_UL-LACDR Fostering the use of omics for grouping and read-across in risk assessment	M37-M81
P5.3.4.b_Y4_RESUPT_RIVM <i>In vitro</i> methods to assess respiratory uptake & toxicity	M37-M81
P6.1.1.e_Y4_FISH-THSD_Uantwerpen An AOP network-based approach for assessing thyroid hormone system disruptors in fish	M37-M81
P6.1.1.f_Y4_HumanRelevance_RIVM Workflow for Human Relevance Assessment of AOPs and Associated New Approach Methodologies	M37-M81
P6.4.1.d_Y4_RE-MIX_UBA_Eawag Options to assess and regulate mixtures	M37-M81
P6.4.2.d_Y4_RegulatoryNAMs_ISS Demonstrating the applicability of NAMs for specific regulatory processes through a series of case studies	M37-M81
P6.4.2.e_Y4_READYAI_UNIBAS Establishment of readiness criteria for AI/ML-based tools used in risk assessment	M37-M81

* Pending approval by GB

Table 3: Projects & case studies planned to end Y4

Project ID	Schedule
P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthCareSurvey_TTL_SRU Occupational survey in the healthcare sector	M1-M48
P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL Occupational survey in the waste management sector	M1-M48
P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based / EDA screening methods for exploring human perinatal exposure to chemicals of emerging concern	M1-M48
P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01-Wastewater based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH Mining chemical information from wastewater treatment plants for I. human community (wastewater fingerprinting for community wide human exposure assessment) and II. environmental exposure assessment (screening of wastewater	M1-M48

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treatment plant effluents to assess the release of Chemicals of Emerging Concern into the water cycle)	
P4.3.4.a_Y2_F02-Food items exposure_ANSES Complementary developments regarding the application of HRMS based/EDA screening methods on food samples	M13-M48
P5.1.1.a_Y1_Toxins_BfR_UNIVIE Hazard characterisation of the mycotoxins enniatins and Alternaria toxins in order to close data gaps and improve risk assessment for human health	M1-M48
P5.2.1.b_Y1_MD-EDC_BfR Metabolic Endocrine Disruption	M1-M48
P5.2.1.c_Y1_EDThDisruption_DTU Endocrine disruptors — Thyroid hormone system disruption	M1-M48
P5.2.1.d_Y1_Immunotox_Inserm Immunotoxicity	M1-M48
P5.2.1.e_Y1_DNT-ANT_UFZ_IUF_NIPH Neurotoxicity	M1-M48
P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR Systems toxicology approaches for mechanism-based chemical safety assessment	M1-M48
P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm AOP Development	M1-M48
P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer PBK models and quantitative systems toxicology	M1-M48
P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_Anses Strategy for aggregate exposure from general life and occupational exposures	M1-M48
P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPk_INERIS_AUTH Refinement and development of PBPK models for human risk assessment	M1-M48
P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM New risk assessment and exposome methodologies to reduce exposure and risk of real-life mixtures	M1-M48
P6.3.1.a_Y1_SubstanceRA_SU Review of substance-specific risk assessment	M1-M48
P6.3.1.a_Y1_SubstanceRA_SU_CS12_MethodOSOA_SU Methods to identify coordination needs towards a 'one substance one assessment' approach	M1-M42
P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI Review of effect-specific risk assessment	M1-M48
P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI_CS11_GenotoxCarc_ISS Analysis and evaluation of genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment across legislations, with a special focus on (Q)SAR based approaches	M1-M48
P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI_CS17_ED-in vitro_BPI Use of non-guideline in vitro studies for ED assessments	M1-M48

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P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI_CS18_ED-classes_BPI New hazard classes and test requirements for endocrine disruption	M1-M48
P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU Review of tools, criteria, and methods used in risk assessment	M1-M48
P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU_CS20_Y3_PESTNAM_ISS Understanding the implementation and use of NAMs in pesticide dossiers in both the Human health and the environment	M25-M48
P6.4.1.a_Y1_OPREMIXCS1_BRUNEL_UGot Optimizing regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe	M1-M40
P6.4.1.b_Y1_MONAMMIXCS2_UFZ Dealing with unknown mixtures in regulatory risk assessments through the use of monitoring data and NAMs	M1-M40

The deliverable D1.10 — AWPY4 can also be reviewed for further details on the activities foreseen during the fourth year.

2.2 Human involvement

Similarly, to the previous years of PARC, the fourth year of PARC will involve human participants.

This can include (i) participants with no link to PARC (ii) participants which are linked to the partnership while external participants (ex: NH, SF or GB members, advisory groups such as IB, etc.) and (iii) individuals working on the PARC partnership from PARC participating organisations.

The profile of these participants can range from volunteers from the wider public in the EU and beyond (in countries with non-EU PARC partners) to individuals who are involved in their professional capacity (ex: representatives from like-minded initiatives, from relevant ministries, from the private sector, from EU agencies, from research organisations, from universities, etc.)

2.2.1 General involvement of external human participants in PARC activities:

As mentioned above, individual external volunteers that are neither part of PARC participating organisations, nor acting on behalf of external organisations will be involved. Their involvement will follow the same two key principles; informed choice and consent. These participants will be duly informed beforehand of the goal of the activities as well as for the ramifications of their participation and will be on a voluntary basis with no penalties for non-participation.

For the activities involving human participants (ex: workshops, consultations, focus groups, etc.), the participation of external participants will be on a volunteer basis and PARC local organisers are expected to obtain and store the individual completed informed consent and local ethics approval (when required). In addition, the informed consent form template (adapted), the information sheet provided to the volunteers and the local ethics approvals will be collected, centralised and stored on the PARC SharePoint.

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The lists below will focus on external participants. Staff from PARC participating organisations which are involved in PARC are considered as being informed and having provided their consent to their participation.

Like during the previous year external participants will be involved in similar generic activities (non-exhaustive list):

- The participation of external reviewers for projects and deliverables;
- The participation in various boards (SF, IB, NH, DEPB, etc.);
- The development of synergies with like-minded initiatives and partners (formal cooperation will be outlined in cooperation / coordination agreements);
- The training activities;
- The dissemination of surveys and focus groups to collect feedback (ex: GB survey, NH survey, specific task / project surveys and focus groups, etc.);
- The organisation of workshops;
- The recruitment of new staff.

For the vast majority of these activities, the collection of samples from volunteers is not invasive / having a significant risk to cause adverse outcomes for the external participants involved. They are below for information.

2.2.2 Involvement of volunteers for HBM studies:

Sampling of matrices from human volunteers (HBM general population survey and targeted survey for waste management sector and healthcare sector) will continue in Y4. The sampling will follow Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) in accordance with the procedures for the PARC Aligned Studies (building on the experience of HBM4EU) developed under T4.1.1.1.

Ethical permissions have been applied for in participating countries. While some participants have yet to submit their ethical dossier in Y3, PARC monitor the submission and approval for each country (see interim progress report of P41.1.12.a for further details). These allow for harmonised and ethical sampling procedures for HBM studies. Indeed, due diligence has been paid (and will continue to be paid) for the collection, use and storage of these materials. This includes the collection of informed consent and ethic authorisations prior to the collection of samples.

Some activities such as the collection of samples under T4.1 will require more invasive procedures (ex: collection of blood). For such activities deemed more invasive, clear procedures have been designed (including the procurement of informed consent from participants) and field workers trained to ensure the respect of external participants volunteers. In parallel, innovative methods (ex: silicone wristbands, dried blood spots) will be tested to provide less-invasive alternatives to participants than classical methods. (Suspect screening (SS), Non targeted screening (NTS) with project P4.3.2.c). QA/QC aspects related to the innovative sampling techniques will be evaluated and included in the design of the add-ons for the HBM surveys.

More specifically and sorted by task, the Y4 ctivities involving external human participants are:

WP1 - Coordination and management
<u>T1.1 - Overall executive management and support of the Partnership:</u> N/A
<u>T1.2 - Scientific steering and implementation of Annual Work Plans:</u> N/A

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T1.3 - Impact evaluation and Monitoring of the performance indicators of the Partnership:

- No activities directly involving external participants have been identified.

T1.4 — Ethics framework:

N/A

WP2 - A common science-policy agenda

T2.1 - Priority setting:

- Dialogue, discussion and feedback with NH, GB (and SF) to define the prioritisation strategy

T2.2- Knowledge Management and uptake to policy:

- Efforts to increase the amount of knowledge shared and co-created by the community on the PARCopedia platform (PARC knowledge management and community platform open to the public launched in Y2 - November 2023)

- Outreach activities of Chemical Leaders/Methodology Leaders (CLs/MLs).

T2.3 - Sustainability:

- Ongoing engagement and development of the National hubs.

WP3 - Synergies, collaborations and awareness

T3.1 — Building effective interactions:

- Management and interaction with the SF and IB (including meetings and collection of feedback / needs).

T3.2 — Communication, dissemination, and awareness:

- Engagement with stakeholders on social media and the PARC website.
- Outreach activities to raise awareness of specific target groups (to be defined).
- Surveys and focus groups to assess citizens' perception and concerns.

T3.3 — Networking and Synergies:

- Continuous update and animation of the SYNnet where external participants with like-minded initiatives can get in contact with PARC to explore collaboration / cooperation opportunities.

WP4 - Monitoring and exposure

T4.1 — Human Biomonitoring:

- Continuation of the EU-wide HBM general population survey including recruitment and sampling (up to ± 3650 children, ± 2750 adolescents and ± 4900 adults) (P4.1.1.2.a).
- Implementation of occupational sectors sampling campaign in the health care sector (samples aiming at 20 hospitals and up to 650 workers) (P4.1.1.4.c)
- Implementation of occupational sectors sampling campaign in the waste sector (samples aiming at 40-50 companies and up to 700 workers) (P4.1.1.4.d)
- Implementation of a mapping exercise to assess the feasibility of a sentinel surveillance system. This mapping exercise includes an engagement assessment of physicians, nurses, employers, workers (P4.1.1.4.b).
- Implementation of targeted surveys (P4.1.1.3.a, P4.1.1.3.b, P4.1.1.3.c) which includes recruitment and sampling from volunteers.

T4.2 - Environmental and multisource monitoring:

- No activities involving external participants have been identified.

T4.3 - Innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys:

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- Recruitment and implementation for a second round of sampling for innovative sampling methods (silicone wristbands, dried blood spots) (P4.3.2.a)

WP5 - Hazard Assessment

T5.1 - Toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern:

- Expert dialogue with representatives from external non-EU- organisations (ex: Health Canada, Ontario University, OECD AOP project) and external EU initiatives (ex: EURION cluster).
- Organisation of workshop with stakeholders for the selection of additives (P5.1.2.c)

T5.2 - Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling:

- No activities involving external participants have been identified.

T5.3 - Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs:

- Discussion on case studies foreseen with regulatory agencies and relevant stakeholders to present progress and obtain feedback.

WP6 - Innovation in regulatory risk assessment

T6.1 - Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment of Chemicals:

- Organisation of stakeholders' workshops on the workflow and the case studies (notably for P6.1.1.a and P6.1.1.b).
- Ongoing Stakeholder engagement with relevant representatives from related research initiatives (ex: ENKORE, EU-ToxRISK, RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX, PrecisionTOX and HESI GTTC), including the participation of external participants in workshops (online and in person)

T6.2 - Integrative exposure and risk assessment:

- Dissemination of deliverables outcomes with external EU regulators from the European Commission (DG SANTE, DG ENVI, DG EMPL.) JRC, and national/regional regulators via webinars and other means of dissemination
- Coordination with data owners to harmonise and upload HBM data in the PARC ToolBox (MCRA) (P6.2.3.a).

T6.3 - Review of risk assessment methodology

- Interviews and surveys targeting experts in chemical RA are foreseen.
- Interaction with stakeholders (ex: SCCS, JRC, OECD,) to refine review and analysis. Possible dissemination to national authorities

T6.4 - Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies

- Structured interviews and surveys targeting experts in chemical RA.
- Organisation of workshops with stakeholders (ex: Kick-off workshop in P6.4.1.d, stakeholder engagement in P6.4.2.d and P6.4.2.e, workshop and coordination activities of P6.4.4.a and P6.4.4.b, etc.)
- Participation of external participants in advisory groups
- Involvement of external participants as beta testers for the tool for assessment of internal validity of in vitro studies: INVITES-IN.

WP7 - FAIR Data

T7.1 - FAIR Data policy and implementation:

- No activities involving external participants have been identified.

T7.2 - Data libraries:

- Collaboration and coordination with representatives from external data platforms/networks (ex: IPCHEM, NORMAN, GENASIS, CPDC).
- Collection of end-users feedback and needs from data hub stakeholders.

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T7.3 - Innovative analyses:

- No activities involving external participants have been identified.

WP8 - Concepts and toolboxes

T8.1 - Safe and sustainable by design (SSbD):

- Dialogue with SSbD stakeholders (EC representatives, industry, scientists and regulators and other EU projects)
- Organisation of workshops focusing on the SSbD toolbox developed (notably with risk assessors and regulators and industry representatives).
- Continuing and deepening the interaction with industry and (internal/external) PARC experts

T8.2 - Scientific and technical basis for an Early warning system (EWS) on chemical risks:

- No activities involving external participants have been identified.

T8.3 - Integrative models:

- No activities involving external participants have been identified.

WP9 - Building infrastructural and human capacities

T9.1 - Laboratory networking:

- Implementation of platform for information exchange and ongoing update of laboratory catalogue

T9.2 - Building exposure monitoring capacities:

- No activities involving external participants have been identified.

T9.3 - Joint activities — harmonisation:

- No activities involving external participants have been identified.

T9.4 — Training:

- Organisation of in-person training courses (including trainings for external stakeholders).

2.3 Human cells/tissues

During Y4, this topic is mostly relevant for WP5, which will require the use of human cells / tissues for the Hazard Assessment with toxicity analyses.

PARC will keep track of the origin of the cells and tissues used, produced or collected. To that end PARC partners that will collect / use / store human cells / tissues have been reminded to obtain the necessary accreditation/designation/authorisation/licensing for using, producing or collecting the cells or tissues as well as the free and fully informed consent of the donors.

The table below provides an overview of the tasks that have been identified as leading to the collection and storage of human cells/tissues.

WP1 - Coordination and management

N/A.

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WP2 - A common science-policy agenda
N/A.
WP3 - Synergies, collaborations and awareness
N/A.
WP4 - Monitoring and exposure
<u>T4.1 – Human Biomonitoring:</u> N/A
<u>T4.2 - Environmental and multisource monitoring:</u> N/A
<u>T4.3 - Innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys:</u> - Proof of concept and performance-assessment of innovative sampling methods (silicone wristbands, dried blood spots in P4.3.2 and P4.3.2.b) and alternative non-invasive matrices (ex: hair or saliva in P4.3.2.c).
WP5 - Hazard Assessment
<u>T5.1 - Toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern:</u> - <i>In-vitro</i> tests relying on human tissues / human cells to close toxicity data gaps mycotoxins & BPA alternatives/analogues.
<u>T5.2 - Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling:</u> - Use of pertinent human cells / tissues to test toxicity in different endpoints and effects (immunotoxicity, non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, (developmental) neurotoxicity, endocrine disruption (thyroid) and metabolic disruption) (ex: BPA alternatives effects on adipocyte; phospholipidosis assay using human liver cells).
<u>T5.3 - Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs:</u> - Use of pertinent human cells / tissues foreseen (e.g. human placenta)
WP6 - Innovation in regulatory risk assessment
N/A
WP7 - FAIR Data
N/A
WP8 - Concepts and toolboxes
N/A
WP9 - Building infrastructural and human capacities
N/A

2.4 Animal experimentation

Animal experimentation in PARC will continue during the fourth year for selected activities. PARC is nevertheless committed to reduce animal testing as much as possible in its activities, in line with the 3 Rs (Replacement, Reduction, Refinement).

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Indeed, PARC activities contributes to the development and use of predictive methods and NAMs which will significantly reduce the need for long-term, low-throughput and costly toxicity tests requiring large numbers of animals, thus contributing to the replacement of animal tests.

Some assays (ex: exposure scenarios) will be conducted on invertebrates (which are not detailed in the table below), such as *Lymnaea stagnalis* (OECD TG 243), *Daphnia magna* (OECD 211), *Nitocra Spinipes*, *xenopus*, *C. elegans* and earthworms.

For other activities, in vivo studies on rodents (rats or mice, TBD) and fishes (zebrafish) are foreseen.

In ongoing project P5.1.2.b, Partner UU (SE) reported problems in carrying out their originally planned experiments (effects on adipocyte development in zebrafish), and as it is taking a long time to get the ethic approvals, they have proposed to determine metabolic rate using Alamar blue assay adapted for zebrafish embryos.

Table 4: Projects starting in Y4 with foreseen animal experimentation:

Project	Animal-based assay	Context	Partner	Project duration
5.1.2.c TG+MP	Bioaccumulation of microplastics and plastic additive Fishes	TG305 studies to assess bioaccumulation of microplastic particles and plastic additives in fish and comparison to freshwater amphipod <i>Hyaella Azteca</i> (for HYBIT test and TG319). The project notably intends to demonstrate the robustness and applicability domain of in vitro bioaccumulation assessment methods which is key to increase their use, reduce the need for vertebrate testing on fish.	ANSES (FR)	M38-M62 (yet to be started)
5.2.1.f DART-ED	Developmental and Reproductive Toxicity - Endocrine Disruption Zebrafish	TG 236 and TG 210 foreseen on zebrafish The methods for the combined evaluation of DART-ED ⁴ in non-mammalian models for environmental health are currently lacking. This project will provide valuable contributions to chemical safety assessors and regulators by delivering evidence-based mechanistic knowledge for DART-ED, facilitating the increased adoption of non-animal test data for ED identification and decision-making	DTU (DK)	M37-M84 (yet to be started)
5.2.1.g DIT-NAM	Developmental immunotoxicity Rodents	Currently, developmental immunotoxicity is assessed by cohort 3 of the Extended One-Generation Reproductive Toxicity (EOGRT) study which is performed in rats. The EOGRT studies are very	INSERM (FR)	M37-M81 (yet to be started)

⁴ DART-ED - Digital, Artificial Intelligence and Robotics Technologies in Education.

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		animal, time and resource intensive. This project will aim to reduce reliance on animal testing by providing alternative methodologies that are fit-for-purpose, efficient and ethically responsible.		
6.1.1.e FISH-THSD	Identification of thyroid hormone system disrupting chemicals (THSDCs) in fish Zebrafish embryo and larvae	For environmental THSDC assessment, mostly amphibian tests are being used (e.g., OECD GD 150, ECHA-EFSA ED Guidance). This project will propose strategies for using these new assays in a tiered ED testing approach for current regulatory contexts and provide a perspective on increased reliance on NAMs and reduced animal testing in line with the EC Roadmap to phase out animal testing for chemical safety assessment	UAntwerpen (BE)	M37-M84 (yet to be started) In vivo assays planned for M53-M80

Below are the activities that foresee animal experimentation (on vertebrates) in the year 4.

WP1 - Coordination and management
N/A.

WP2 - A common science-policy agenda
N/A.

WP3 - Synergies, collaborations and awareness
N/A.

WP4 - Monitoring and exposure
<u>N/A</u>

WP5 - Hazard Assessment
<p><u>T5.1 - Toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Animal experimentation on rats with the implementation of an OECD TG408 (Repeated Dose 90-Day Oral Toxicity Study in Rodents) to fill an <i>in vivo</i> data gap on Enniatin B1 (P5.1.1.c). - Animal experimentation on fishes with the implementation of an OECD TG 229 (or TG 230) (Fish short-term reproduction assay) to investigate the potential ED related effects of “real-life” mixtures of BPA alternatives on different species of organisms (P5.1.2.b) <p><u>T5.2 - Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Animal experimentation on zebrafish as whole organism model to optimise the protocols and identify most suitable timepoints of analysis (P5.2.1.a).

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- Animal experimentation on rats for a rodent reproductive toxicity study. A toxicogenomic comparison between *in vivo* effects in the developing rat liver and in the human stem cell-based hepatocyte *in vitro* assay will be performed to assess cross-species and assay translatability (P5.2.1.c).
- Animal experimentation on zebrafish and snail assays with metformin and BPE
- Animal experimentation on mice with a respiratory sensitisation. Mice exposure to known respiratory sensitizer chemicals to induce respiratory allergy in order to establish the doses for sensitisation assays (P5.2.1.d).
- Animal experimentation on mice as an experimental model of response to vaccination. The response to an influenza vaccine of mice will be monitored in the presence or absence of chemicals (toxins, PFAS) (P5.2.1.d).
- Animal experimentation on zebrafish (P5.2.1.f) for endocrine disruptor strengthening and expansion of the assay (cross-species extrapolation potential)

T5.3 - Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs:

- Animal experimentation on rats to assess exposure to Enniatin B (P5.3.4.a).

WP6 - Innovation in regulatory risk assessment

N/A

WP7 - FAIR Data

N/A

WP8 - Concepts and toolboxes

N/A

WP9 - Building infrastructural and human capacities

N/A

2.5 Data use and processing

PARC is well aware of the GDPR which codify the management and use of all personal data across EU. The partnership's use and processing of data will comply with the obligations outlined in the regulation.

Like previous years, PARC activities during the fourth year will include the collection and use of personal data for the realisation of the activities of the partnership including sensitive personal data (specifically genetic data, health-related data and biometric data).

This can include personal data necessary for the management of the partnership (ex: meeting registration information, contact email for administrative purpose, etc.) across all PARC activities, but also more sensitive data such as the collection, processing and storage of health data in the framework of the HBM surveys. PARC partners are aware of the sensitivity of this data use and processing. Appropriate procedures have been set-up to prevent or minimise possible adverse impact on the individuals. This notably includes the collection of informed consent from participants for both the direct use of the results, as well as the possible reuse of their health data and inclusion in a biobank. In addition, a data management team (VITO, MU, SPF, UBA, TTL, PIH) will further support all HBM related data management activities in T4.1.

Furthermore, PARC will also (where feasible) anonymise or pseudonymise personal health data of volunteers to limit the possible impact of the data generated / processed on the individuals concerned.

The processing and the analysis of the data generated from the HBM surveys and from the standardised health measurements that had started in Y2 will continue during Y4.

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To facilitate the management of data produced under PARC, an agreement on transfer of personal data from data controllers to the JRC (on the IPCHEM portal) as a joint-controller or controller is under preparation in Y3-Y4.

In parallel, discussions and due diligence to allow the reuse of data from other projects/researchers as well as to make PARC data FAIR will continue during Y4.

Indeed, while PARC's activities will generate its own data, it will also make use of pre-existing datasets (ex: HMB4EU data). PARC partners will follow process to access these datasets through the procurement of the agreement of respective data owners (and when necessary / possible of the participants).

Highlight on P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO and data management framework:

Data generated by the project:

Individual data will be generated via the P4.1.1.2.a project i.e., individual level (pseudonymous) human biomonitoring data (internal exposure and effect biomarker levels), associated lifestyle and personal information, and possibly external exposure data, collected from HBM studies in Europe co-funded by PARC. Data management aspects related to these data will be defined in the joint T4.1/T7.1 project on 'FAIR and sustainable storage of HBM data starting in year 1. Personal information will be collected from survey participants via questionnaires, analytical results will be provided by the analysing laboratories through the study principal investigators.

Individual level (pseudonymous) data will be made available via PEH platform [Personal Exposure and Health Data Platform; central data platform developed and managed by VITO during the HBM4EU project].

Use of individual level data only after approval of data access request by the DRAC (= data request access committee) linked to the PEH platform and meta data can be accessed via dashboard hosted by VITO or IPCHEM hosted by JRC.

Exposure data metadata will be hosted on IPCHEM (available to the PARC consortium and EU agencies during the PARC project; publicly accessible after the PARC project) and aggregated data will be hosted on an online user-friendly HBM dashboard (on the PEH platform from VITO mentioned above).

Access to individual HBM data (pseudonymous data) via the central data platform will be granted after approval of the request by the DRAC (Data Request Access Committee). An embargo period will be defined for access by parties external to PARC.

External exposure information (e.g. in environmental matrices, food and products) and health status data collected by or generated (via measurement or modelling) in other projects in WP4 or WP6 may be used in this project to link them to human biomonitoring data. Such data should be findable and accessible to the project partners.

In particular, the following task has been identified for sensitive data use, data re-use or data processing in Y3:

WP1 - Coordination and management

Transversal:

- Overall communication to PARC partners and external contacts which requires the collection and processing of personal data.
- Collection and processing of personal data for the organisation of meetings

T1.1 - Overall executive management and support of the Partnership:

- No specific activities involving the use of sensitive data has been identified.

T1.2 - Scientific steering and implementation of Annual Work Plans:

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- No specific activities involving the use of sensitive data has been identified.

T1.3 - Impact evaluation and Monitoring of the performance indicators of the Partnership:

- No specific activities involving the use of sensitive data has been identified.

T1.4 — Ethics framework:

- No specific activities involving the use of sensitive data has been identified.

WP2 - A common science-policy agenda

Transversal:

- Overall communication to PARC partners and external contacts which requires the collection and processing of personal data.

- Collection and processing of personal data for the organisation of meetings

T2.1 - Priority setting:

- No specific activities involving the use of sensitive data has been identified.

T2.2- Knowledge Management:

- The population of the PARCopedia platform (PARC knowledge management and community platform) which will process and store data generated in PARC in others WPs and allow the possibility for users to upload external data (provided that they are legally allowed to do so).

T2.3 - Sustainability:

- No specific activities involving the use of sensitive data has been identified.

WP3 - Synergies, collaborations and awareness

Transversal:

- Overall communication to PARC partners and external contacts which requires the collection and processing of personal data.

- Collection and processing of personal data for the organisation of meetings & workshops

T3.1 — Building effective interactions:

- No specific activities involving the use of sensitive data has been identified.

T3.2 — Communication, dissemination, and awareness:

- No specific activities involving the use of sensitive data has been identified.

T3.3 — Networking and Synergies:

- No specific activities involving the use of sensitive data has been identified.

WP4 - Monitoring and exposure

Transversal:

- Overall communication to PARC partners and external contacts which requires the collection and processing of personal data.

- Collection and processing of personal data for the organisation of meetings & workshops

T4.1 — Human Biomonitoring:

- Finalisation of the collection of ethics approval before the start of activities in participating countries (for countries where the ethics authorisation application process is still ongoing).

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- Continuation of the EU-wide HBM general population survey which leads to the collection of sensitive health data from volunteers (P4.1.1.2.a) (see above for further details).
- Implementation of occupational sectors surveys in the healthcare sector including the collection of sensitive health data from volunteers (P4.1.1.4.c). Currently 6 countries have already got ethical permission (PL, GR, FI, IT, BE, SE) to proceed.
- Implementation of occupational sectors surveys including recruitment and sampling in the waste sector the collection of sensitive health data from volunteers (P4.1.1.4.d). Currently Latvia has received ethical permission to proceed and other partners from participating countries are in the process of application.
- Preparation of a joint controllership agreement with JRC to centralise the management of the data collected in the HBM studies under T4.1 on the IPCHEM platform.
- Overall data coding, data harmonisation and statistical analysis on collected samples for general HBM survey (P4.1.1.2.a) and targeted surveys (P4.1.1.3.a, P4.1.1.3.b, P4.1.1.3.c) and occupational surveys (P4.1.1.4.c, P4.1.1.4.d)
- Analysis of health data (anonymised / pseudonymised) to derive HBM guidance values (P4.1.3.1.a).
- Re-use of existing health data (from samples collected in cohorts / biobanks) to quantify past exposures and link them to effect biomarkers and health outcomes (P4.1.3.3.a). This also foresees further analysis of biological samples stored in biobanks.

T4.2 - Environmental and multisource monitoring:

- Analysis of pre-existing data as well as of data generated in PARC (use and processing of health data).

T4.3 - Innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys:

- Use and processing of data generated in PARC to support the development of early warning system (P4.3.1.c). In Y4, a reinforced focus will be operated to formulate a set of operational criteria for the categorization of annotated data to be integrated in the EWS format, as a basis to further elaborate a global decision tree aiming at guiding the way from the lab data to the useful support to policy with regard to these new innovative methodological approaches.
- Use of existing data-set (including HBM data) to evaluate data processing strategies and parametrisation (P4.3.1.d) in order to develop a comprehensive, user-friendly and semi-automated pipeline for suspect screening (SS) / non-target screening (NTS) / Effect-Directed Analysis (EDA) related data processing. In Y4, the generation of tools for the automatization of the suspect screening will be validated and valorised
- Comparison and analysis of data generated in PARC from innovative sampling methods and conventional approaches (P4.3.2.a, P4.3.2.b and P4.3.2.c). During Y4, after generating and compiling the results from the chemical SS/NTS profiling of urine, blood, and maternal milk samples from the 30 pregnant women, an extensive and comprehensive data analysis will be conducted and the results combined with the findings from the inter-lab assay.

WP5 - Hazard Assessment

Transversal:

- Overall communication to PARC partners and external contacts which requires the collection and processing of personal data.
- Collection and processing of personal data for the organisation of meetings & workshops

T5.1 - Toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern:

- No specific activities involving the use of sensitive data has been identified.

T5.2 - Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling:

- No specific activities involving the use of sensitive data has been identified.

T5.3 - Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs:

- No specific activities involving the use of sensitive data has been identified.

WP6 - Innovation in regulatory risk assessment

DELIVERABLE D10.4

Transversal:

- Overall communication to PARC partners and external contacts which requires the collection and processing of personal data.
- Collection and processing of personal data for the organisation of meetings & workshops.

T6.1 - Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment of Chemicals:

- No specific activities involving the use of sensitive data has been identified.

T6.2 - Integrative exposure and risk assessment:

- Some T6.2 activities may analyse and process health data (pseudonymised data) during Y4 from several HBM dataset from different European general and occupational populations (ex: P6.2.1.a; P6.2.1.b), for instance to perform mixture RA or to verify the outcomes of models developed.
- Reuse of data generated in PARC for extensive parameterisation will continue in Y4 (P6.2.2.a), this will notably tackle sensitive data with the impact of bioavailability differences related to age, gender and route of exposure.
- Further work on harmonisation and upload of data in PARCToolBox (MCRA) for the remaining HBM data (P6.2.3.a) in Y4.
- A review of newly available health impact assessments and environmental burden of disease calculations, exposure data, and exposure-effect functions necessary for the case studies will be performed in Y3 (P6.2.4.a; P6.2.4.b).

T6.3 - Review of risk assessment methodology

- No specific activities involving the use of sensitive data has been identified.

T6.4 - Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies

- No specific activities involving the use of sensitive data has been identified.

WP7 - FAIR Data

Transversal:

- Overall communication to PARC partners and external contacts which requires the collection and processing of personal data.
- Collection and processing of personal data for the organisation of meetings, training & workshops.

T7.1 - FAIR Data policy and implementation:

-
- No specific activities involving the use of sensitive data has been identified.

T7.2 - Data libraries:

- Data review, analysis and processing to harmonise metadata (exchange templates, standards, vocabularies, etc.)n coordination with external data platforms/networks (e.g.: IPCHEM, NORMAN, GENASIS, Elixir).
- Development of pipelines for datasets sharing.
- Coordination with WP4, WP6 and WP8 for the FAIRification of HBM datasets. Includes further use of existing health data and data processing (e.g., transfer of HBM4EU data to PARC).

T7.3 - Innovative analyses:

- No specific activities involving the use of sensitive data has been identified.

WP8 - Concepts and toolboxes

Transversal:

- Overall communication to PARC partners and external contacts which requires the collection and processing of personal data.
- Collection and processing of personal data for the organisation of meetings, training & workshops.

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T8.1 - Safe and sustainable by design (SSbD):

- No specific activities involving the use of sensitive data has been identified.

T8.2 - Scientific and technical basis for an Early warning system (EWS) on chemical risks:

- Development of EWS which will include HBM data (in collaboration with WP4). To function, this will require use processing and analysis of sensitive health and personal data. For instance, in Y4 Mixture toxicity data from human and ecotoxicity will be linked to NTS data which is then foreseen to be uploaded to digital data banks, (e.g., NORMAN digital sampling freezing platform).

T8.3 - Integrative models:

- Development of integrative models (notably exposure assessment models which includes HBM data analysis) To be developed, tested, and to function, this will require use processing and analysis of sensitive health and personal data.

WP9 - Building infrastructural and human capacities

Transversal:

- Overall communication to PARC partners and external contacts which requires the collection and processing of personal data.
- Collection and processing of personal data for the organisation of meetings, training & workshops.

T9.1 - Laboratory networking:

- No specific activities involving the use of sensitive data has been identified.

T9.2 - Building exposure monitoring capacities:

- No specific activities involving the use of sensitive data has been identified.

T9.3 - Joint activities — harmonisation:

- No specific activities involving the use of sensitive data has been identified.

T9.4 — Training:

- No specific activities involving the use of sensitive data has been identified.

2.6 Artificial Intelligence

Some PARC research activities leverage ML and Artificial Intelligence (AI/ML). No sensitive AI activities have been identified up to now.

AI can be a valuable tool to empower chemical RA, provided it is used as a support tool (and not decision-making tool) by researchers and policymakers, and provided that any possible bias (e.g., use of biased datasets) are adequately addressed and corrected for, and the included / excluded data fully documented and justified.

For example, text-mining is showing promise as it allows for the automated extraction and analysis of large amounts of information from various sources, which can help to identify potential hazards early on, extract information on chemical properties, identify potential exposure pathways, extract information on regulations and policies, and identify potential alternative materials. AI-powered computational algorithms can be used to analyse large amounts of data, including sensor readings and weather patterns, helping to identify outliers and anomalies that may indicate a chemical incident. Furthermore, AI can be used to predict the impact that a chemical might have on human health and the environment, helping to improve response times and reduce the risk of harm. In the list below, we focus on the use of AI directly related to research activities in year 4

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PARC will build on the highlighted interest of the PARC DEPB and the PARC GB on AI/ML. T1.4 aims to organise an initial meeting with relevant PARC participants to better assess how AI/ML are used in PARC, and to discuss more detailed guidelines to follow. The outcome of this assessment and discussion is expected to be reported to the PARC GB during a dedicated workshop in Y4.

WP1 - Coordination and management

T1.4 - Ethics Framework:

- Assessment of AI/ML use in PARC and follow-up meeting to be organised with relevant PARC partners to ensure a responsible use in PARC activities.
- Organisation of a follow-up dedicated workshop on AI/ML use for Chemical RA for the GB members.

WP2 - A common science-policy agenda

N/A.

WP3 - Synergies, collaborations and awareness

N/A.

WP4 - Monitoring and exposure

T4.1 – Human Biomonitoring:

- No relevant activities have been identified.

T4.2 - Environmental and multisource monitoring:

- No relevant activities have been identified.

T4.3 - Innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys:

- Establishment of necessary advanced data processing methodologies and bioinformatic tools (P4.3.1.d)

WP5 - Hazard Assessment

T5.1 - Toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern:

- No relevant activities have been identified.

T5.2 - Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling:

- No relevant activities have been identified.

T5.3 - Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs:

- Validation of innovative *in silico* and bioinformatics approaches for quantitative chemical hazard assessment (P5.3.1.a)
- Development of protocols and tools to optimize and harmonize data collection, appraisal, synthesis and visualization based on artificial intelligence supporting AOP development [AI and text mining tools development] (P5.3.2.a)

WP6 - Innovation in regulatory risk assessment

T6.1 - Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment of Chemicals:

- No relevant activities have been identified.

T6.2 - Integrative exposure and risk assessment:

- No relevant activities have been identified.

T6.3 - Review of risk assessment methodology

- No relevant activities have been identified.

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T6.4 - Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies

- Review and analysis of the AI and ML QSAR models and to identify best practices and further actions to ensure a transparent regulatory use (P6.4.2.c)
- Establishment of readiness criteria for Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning (AI/ML)-based tools for supporting the RA process (P6.4.2.e).

WP7 - FAIR Data

T7.1 - FAIR Data policy and implementation:

- Review of the PARC Fair Data Policy using AI models on internet resources and text-mining approaches (as part of the DPM update)

T7.2 - Data libraries:

- No relevant activities have been identified.

T7.3 - Innovative analyses:

- Case study to understand the long-term impact of chemical mixtures on biodiversity and ecosystem functions by leveraging lake sedimentary archives, paleoecotoxicology and AI-based forecasting.
- Use case to derive health outcomes from epidemiological data, human biomonitoring data and metabolomics data using ML approaches.
- Development of an ontology-based text-mining and data integration scheme for the classification and storage of information about chemical hazards and RA (P7.3.3.a). In Y4 the case studies initiated in Year 3 will continue, providing further insights to optimize the text mining system and clarify requirements.
- Development of an automated ontology naming application which would rely on existing datasets (e.g., DisGeNET) and text mining on literature and clinical trials (P7.3.3.a)
- Use of machine-learning to power modelling for screening Blood Brain Barrier permeation of xenobiotics.
- [Indirect] Scoping study of AI&ML-driven computational NAMs for use in NGRA (P7.3.4.b).
- Development of ML and deep learning models to predict the fraction unbound in plasma based on critical structural features of chemicals (P7.3.4.c)

WP8 - Concepts and toolboxes

T8.1 - Safe and sustainable by design (SSbD):

- No relevant activities have been identified.

T8.2 - Scientific and technical basis for an Early warning system (EWS) on chemical risks:

- Implementation of a ML driven non-targeted approach to evaluate early warning signals of chemical compounds in food for emerging risk identification.

T8.3 - Integrative models:

- No relevant activities have been identified.

WP9 - Building infrastructural and human capacities

N/A

2.7 Environment, health and safety

No actions with significant detrimental effects on the environment are foreseen. As PARC is a partnership focused on chemical RA and management, some activities (notably in toxicology) may include the use / collection / manipulation of chemicals which may be harmful for the environment or for the health of researchers if not handled correctly, though they are not on a scale which could have significant negative consequences. Indeed,

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assessing their impact on the environment and human health cannot be done without the legitimate use of these chemicals during analysis and other research activities.

For these activities, strict SOPs have been designed to safeguard from potential risk for the environment or for the health of researchers involved (as well as for other individuals that may be involved).

With regards to environment, health and safety, PARC is instead designed to better understand and better address the risks posed by chemicals for the environment, health and safety of EU citizens. For instance, actions designed to monitor environmental exposure are planned in year 4. In addition, work under T8.2 led to the development of a report (D8.2) outlining the PARC EWS concept. The PARC EWS is intended to be a decision-making tool that will use various data sources to monitor potential risks and provide early alerts to regulator with a comprehensive scope that includes coverage of a wide range of hazards, geographic areas, sectors, data sources, stakeholders, and time. This will ensure that it can detect and respond to potential risks in a timely and effective manner and provide decision-makers with the information they need to mitigate or prevent the impact of hazards on communities and the environment

Pilot studies started in Y2 for the monitoring of PFAS in freshwater and endocrine disruptors in different environmental compartments will continue. Likewise, the T4.3 project initiated in Y2 to monitor chemicals of concern in wastewater with the development of innovative methods based on suspect screening, non-targeted screening and effect-directed analysis will continue in Y4.

2.8 Involvement of non-EU countries

Non-EU countries have been involved in the activities of PARC from the first year of PARC (Iceland, Norway, Switzerland, Israel, UK) across all WPs. PARC participants are aware that they have to ensure that the activities performed in non-EU-countries will remain in line with at least one EU member state's legislations.

Local ethics approvals are needed for PARC activities taking place in non-EU countries.

In addition, collaboration and networking is not limited by the EU boundaries over the duration of PARC. Involvement of experts is also valid for countries in the wider European region and OECD countries.

For instance, the IB set up in the first year includes non-EU members from the United States, Canada, Japan and South Africa.

3 Conclusion

As it stands, PARC has been using the first three years of the partnership to set-up its ethics processes and make sure that all participants are aware of their obligations and have the necessary support/guidance to implement them. Further Ethics training and resources for PARC members are foreseen in Y4.

To the best of our knowledge, no significant ethics issues have arisen in the third year and none have been specifically identified for Y4 (which do not have mitigation measures / oversight processes already implemented). Ethics good practices have been followed for the few elements of concern identified in line with the PARC internal ethics guidelines which has been developed and finalised during Y2.

Of course, caution is to be observed during the fourth year of PARC, and the PARC consortium will further review the work (and potential) of AI/ML for Chemical RA activities in PARC.

No other specific possible issues have been identified, but PARC members will remain vigilant.

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Annex:

Annex 1 – Ethics project assessment

Legend:

	Finished projects
	New projects

		Project acronym	Ethics referent											
			hESCs involvement	Respect national and EU legislations	Involve human participants	Use of human cells/tissues	Use and process personal data	animal research/testing	Non-EU countries involvement	Use of Artificial Intelligence	Use of potentially harmful substances			
Started Y1	WP4	P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMsurvey_VITO	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	liese.gilles@vito.be		
		P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasibility_TTL	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	tiina.santonen@ttl.fi		
		P4.1.1.4.b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	lode.godderis@kuleuven.be		
		P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthCareSurvey_TTL_RUMC	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	paul.scheepers@radboudumc.nl		
		P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	tiina.santonen@ttl.fi		
		P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_DerivationofHBM-GVs_UBA	No		No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	Petra.apel@uba.de		
		P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VI	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Hardiesse.BESSONNEAU@santepubliquefran		
		P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	parc@vito.be		
		P4.1.5.a_Y1_SustainHBMSystem_VITO	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	parc@vito.be		
		P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	kvo@envs.au.dk; Valeria.dulio@ineris.fr		
		P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01-Concept Paper_MU	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	elliott.price@recetox.muni.cz		
		P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02-QAQC_WR	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Hans.mo@wur.nl		
	P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03-EWStools_SLU	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Lutz.ahrens@slu.se			
	P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04-Data Processing Worflow_EHESP	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Arthur.david@ehesp.fr			
	P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	jean-philippe.antignac@inrae.fr			
	P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01-Wastewater based epidemiology	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	werner.brack@ufz.de			
	WP5	P5.1.1.a_Y1_Toxins_BFR_UNIVIE	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	doris.marko@univie.ac.at; jessica.dietrich@t		
		P5.1.1.b_Y1_BPA_HumTox_BFR	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	emanuela.testai@iss.it		
		P5.1.2.a_Y1_NaturalToxinsAqua_Ugent	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Jana.asselmann@ugent.be		
		P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	ludek.blaha@recetox.muni.cz; ondrej.adamo		
		P5.2.1.a_Y1_NGTxCs_INRAE	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	marc.audebert@inrae.fr; Michael.Oelgeschla		
		P5.2.1.b_Y1_MD-EDC_INRAE	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	daniel.zalko@inrae.fr		
		P5.2.1.c_Y1_EDThDisruption_DTU	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	tesv@food.dtu.dk; Tamara.Vanhaecke@vub.		
		P5.2.1.d_Y1_Immunotox_Inserm	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	robert.barouki@u-paris.fr; etienne.blanc@u-		
P5.2.1.e_Y1_Neurotox_UFZ_IUF_UU		No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	tamara.tal@ufz.de; ellen.fritsche@iuf-duesse			
P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR		No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	b.water@lacr.leidenuniv.nl			
P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm		No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	adelheid.soubry@kuleuven.be			
P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer		No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	sylyia.escher@item.fraunhofer.de			
WP6	P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	Mirjam.Luijten@rivm.nl			
	P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA-ED_Uantwerpen	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	dries.knapen@uantwerpen.be			
	P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	birgit.mertens@sciensano.be			
	P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	b.water@lacr.leidenuniv.nl			
	P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Katleen.debrouwere@vito.be			
	P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_AnseS	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	amelie.crepet@anses.fr			
	P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPk_INERIS_AUTH	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	spyrsk@auth.gr			
	P6.2.3.a_Y1_ReallifeMixtures_RIVM	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	jacob.van.klaveren@rivm.nl			
	P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADDataAvailability_VITO	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	J.J.Vlaanderen@uu.nl; j.j.vlaanderen@uu.			
	P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	J.J.Vlaanderen@uu.nl; J.J.Vlaanderen@vito.			
	P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_UU-IRAS	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	J.J.Vlaanderen@uu.nl; J.J.Vlaanderen@vito.			
	P6.2.4.d_Y1_HIAIndicators_VITO	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	J.J.Vlaanderen@uu.nl; J.J.Vlaanderen@vito.			
WP7	P6.3.1.a_Y1_SubstanceRA_SU	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	marlene.agerstrand@aces.su.se			
	P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	d.nikolopolou@bpi.gr			
	P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	marlene.agerstrand@aces.su.se			
	P6.4.1.a_Y1_OPREMIACS1_BRUNEL_UGot	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	thomas.backhaus@gu.se; andreas.kortenka			
	P6.4.1.b_Y1_MONAMMIXCS2_UFZ	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	Wibke.busch@ufz.de; veronika.plichta@ages			
	P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurv_UNIBAS	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	angela.beath@hest.ethz.ch			
	P6.4.2.b_Y1_NGRApractice_VKM_NIPH	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	Gro.haarklou.mathisen@vkm.no			
	P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	uko.maran@ut.ee			
	P6.4.3.a_Y1_SuProm_MU	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	lisa.melymuk@recetox.muni.cz			
	P6.4.4.a_Y1_CRNCS1_KEMI	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Johan.axelman@kemi.se			
	P6.4.4.b_Y1_PPPEPCXS2_SLU	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Mikaela.Goncz@slu.se			
	P6.4.4.c_Y1_PPPEFFCS3_UFZ	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	matthias.liess@ufz.de			
Started Y2	WP4	P6.4.4.d_Y1_PPPEFFCS3_UKOLD	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	schaefer-raif@uni-landau.de		
		P6.4.4.e_Y1_PPPOSCSS_ISCIII	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Jtarazona@isciii.es		
		P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Richard.hulek@recetox.muni.cz		
		P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatsets_VITO	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Jan.theunis@vito.be		
		P7.3.3.a_Y1_ALT-IST_ISTSPV	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	vikas.kumar@urv.cat		
		P4.2.b_Y2_Monitoringframe_AU_INERIS	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	kvo@envs.au.dk; Valeria.dulio@ineris.fr		
		P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02-Occupational exposure_INRS	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	sophie.ndaw@inrs.fr; Radu.duca@ins.etat.lu		
		P4.3.3.b_Y2_E02-Sentinel animals_ONIRIS	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	ronan.carriou@oniris-nantes.fr		
		P4.3.4.a_Y2_F02-Food items exposure_ANSES	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	julien.parinet@anses.fr		
		P.2.1.a_Y3MnHexP-RRM_UBA	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	Till.Weber@uba.de		
		Started Y3	WP4	P4.2.c_Y3_Human exposure_INERIS_AU	No	Yes	No	No	TBD	No	Yes	No	TBD	kvo@envs.au.dk; Valeria.dulio@ineris.fr
				P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03-Complementarydevelopments_JS	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	tina.kosjek@ijs.si; alexander.vannuijs@uant
P5.1.1.c_Y3_TG+EnnB1_ANSES	No			Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	thalia.decastelbajac@anses.fr; gilles.RIVIERE		
P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_CS20_Y3_PESTNAM_ISS	No			Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	emma.diconsiglio@iss.it		
P6.4.1.c_Y3_Skinsenmix_RegionH	No			Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	TBD	No	TBD	Jeanne.Duus.Johansen@regionh.dk		
P6.4.3.b_Y3_ENFORCE_Kemi	No			Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	Robin.vestergren@kemi.se; lisa.melymuk@re		
P4.1.1.3.a_Y4_PFA5_mother_milk_LNS_BPI	No			Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	TBD	k.kasiotis@bpi.gr; Maria.TorresToda@lins.eta		
P4.1.1.3.b_Y4_PFA5Children_SpF	No			Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	loic.rambaud@santepubliquefrance.fr		
P4.1.1.3.c_Y4_TimePatternEU_VITO	No			Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	hamid.hassen@vito.be		
P4.1.3.1.b_Y4_Health-based-IA-GV_LNS_NCPHP	No			Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	ruth.moeller@lins.etat.lu		
P4.2.d_Y4_Siloxanes_AU_INERIS	No			Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	kvo@envs.au.dk; Valeria.dulio@ineris.fr		
Started Y4	WP5			P5.1.1.d_Y4_PlasticLeach_NIPH	No	Yes	No	TBD	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	sloureiro@ua.pt
		P5.1.2.c_Y4_TG+MP_ANSES	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	thalia.decastelbajac@anses.fr		
		P5.2.1.f_Y4_DART-ED_DTU	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	tesv@food.dtu.dk		
		P5.2.1.g_Y4_DIT-NAM_INSERM	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	saadia.kerdine-romer@universite-paris-sacla		
		P5.2.1.h_Y4_SDEHPATOX_ANSES	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	estelle.dubreil@anses.fr; ludovic.lehgarat@		
		P5.2.a_Y4_RegNAMs_ANSES	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	Gilles.RIVIERE@anses.fr		
		P5.3.1.b_Y4_gROMICS_UL-LACDR	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	g.callegaro@lacr.leidenuniv.nl		
		P5.3.4.b_Y4_RESUPT_RIVM	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yvonne.Staal@RIVM.nl		
		P6.1.1.e_Y4_FISH-THSD_Uantwerpen	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	dries.knapen@uantwerpen.be		
		P6.1.1.f_Y4_HumanRelevance_RIVM	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	Mirjam.Luijten@rivm.nl		
		P6.4.1.d_Y4_RE-MIX_UBA_Eawag	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	enken.hassold@uba.de		
		P6.4.2.d_Y4_RegulatoryNAMs_ISS	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	emma.diconsiglio@iss.it		
P6.4.2.e_Y4_READYAI_UNIBAS	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	TBD	No	ellen.fritsche@unibas.ch				